

The Impact of Drug Abuse on Society: A Review on Drug Abuse in the Context of Society

Aishatu Musa Yusuf
Department of Public Administration.
Fed..Polytechnic. Damaturu, Yobe State

Salehumar
Department. of Office Tech And Management
Fed. Polytechnic. Damaturu, Yobe State

Abstract:- Drug addiction is defined by an uncontrollable and persistent desire to seek and consume the drug. Due to developments in the understanding of mechanisms involved as well as the need for more precision in definition, drug nomenclature has developed over time. Drug addiction is caused by how drugs of consumption interact with each individual's neurobehavioral constitution, as well as their pharmacological consequences. The study of the neural molecular mechanisms addiction processes allows for a better understanding of current pharmacotherapy as well as the development of novel drug misuse and dependency treatment options. In this work, we want to present recent ideas about abuse and addiction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse has become so widespread that it is a major issue for people all over the world. Today's youth is often associated with high aspiration, a fast-paced lifestyle, and celebrity, however, drug addiction has become so widely spread that it is a significant issue for individuals all over the globe [1]. A million people die each year as a result of cigarettes, alcohol, and illicit drug use. The threat of drug addiction develops in our culture with each passing day. The most terrible aspect of the situation is that the country's youth have surrendered to these temptations. Today's society has become very familiar with the damage caused by drug abuse amongst young students. Medications have an impact on a person's brain, brain, lungs, abilities, and mental health [2]. In a number of countries, both established and developing, the expenditures associated with drug use continue to hold a pressure on social systems. Drug abuse among young adults is dangerous and frequent, prompting efforts to raise awareness of the negative consequences and change attitudes.

A young man's home setting is where he or she spends the majority of his or her time. He is taught social, artistic, cultural, and standards of morality, as well as other virtues like kindness and obedience, and he is aware of the behavior of his parents and siblings, which has influenced his own attitude, pattern, and habits. Those values he learned as a child from his parents have influenced him throughout his life. The child also learns what is bad and what is right from their family surroundings, the home environment is described [3]. As a measure of how dedicated, helpful, and supportive members of the family are to one another. Among the most significant aspects of the living environment is the emotional stability offered by parents and family, as it supports in the child's actual functioning and balanced growth. Parents' actions have a huge impact on their

parenting choices. The hopes, worries, and experiences of their children are heavily influenced by their parents. At home, overly controlling or inattentive parents may support their kids to become excited about and attracted to negative behaviors, such as drug use. There are just not enough policy decisions, and there aren't enough resources. Increased drug addiction among adolescents, specifically those in between ages of 16 and 19, can be ascribed to a greater understanding of the negative effects of drugs as well as a poor home environment. The two parts of "maternal love compassion" and success, according to [4], are anticipation, demand, and requirements.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE DRUG ADDICTION ABUSE

- **What are Drugs?** Drugs are compounds that alter the physical or mental functioning of the body. These substances might be natural, like cocaine, or semi-synthetic along with cocaine and euphoria, or prednisone, which is fully synthetic. All of the drugs mentioned in this article have a pharmacological or psychiatric effect on the brain, making them psychotropic or psychotropic [5]. These mood-altering drugs have an effect on our thoughts, actions, and emotions. We believe that people use drugs for negative reasons, such as being miserable or dissatisfied. etc. - but we forget that the majority of drug users derive a lot of pleasure and delight from the drugs they take. However, the pleasure and delight come at a cost, as all drug usage is fraught with dangers. There has never been and will never be a medicine that is completely safe. Even though most drug addicts consume their substance for its mental benefits, it also has side effects on other parts of the body, hence physical effects are concern.
- **Drug Types:** Although all of these psychoactive substances do have mind as their prime objective, their impacts and body are diverse. Depressants like alcohol, for example, slow the brain, but stimulants like cocaine and amphetamine physically speed up the body [6]. Heroin-type narcotics are potent pain relievers that also induce sleep. Hallucinogens are a class of medicines that produce complex mental experiences, such as LSD ('Acid'). There are, however, medications that do not cleanly fall into a single category, marijuana is the most often used illegal product, but it's also one of the most complicated, as it's made up of over 300 distinct substances, some of which have opposing physical effects [7]. If consumed in massive levels, it can cause euphoria, depression, and delusions.
- **Drug-Related Issues:** There is a tendency to think about drug dangers in very restricted terms at times. Addiction/overdoses, as well as HIV and AIDS, have received a lot of attention recently. Such a focus

could be deceptive, both in terms of assessing the dangers of a specific substance and in terms of attempting to return positively to problem [8]. As either an outcome, a broad understanding of what constitutes a drug-related problem is required, including not only the apparent addiction, but also the ideas of drug-related illness, narcotic crime, drugs in pregnancy, the impact of drugs on learning and work, and the influence of drugs on traffic incidents and behaviour patterns.

- **Alcoholism:** Alcoholism, also referred as drug dependency, is the persistent use of a chemical on a regular basis in order to experience its psychoactive effects or to avoid the discomfort of its absence. Other types of dependency exist, such as opioid addiction, alcoholism, and so on. Compulsive drug use develops after frequent exposure to a variety of drugs. Alcohol, tranquilizers, nicotine, and cocaine are all examples of opiates. The reliance might be physical or mental [9].
- **Overdose deaths and Sudden Death:** Another usual approach of evaluating a drug is to question whether it will cause death if you take too much of it. Binging on some drugs, such as heroin, cocaine, and alcohol, can be fatal. Solvents, for example, can induce abrupt death. Drugs and Sudden Cardiac death: Another classic method of appraising a medicine is to ask if it will kill you if you consume it, take too much of it. Overdosing on some drugs, such as heroin, cocaine, and alcohol, can be fatal. Solvents, for example, can induce abrupt death[10]. It's the latter that's the most tough to handle. Because regular exposure to the substance is common, The most serious problem that a druggie might confront is addiction. Although some drugs, such as LSD, are not highly addictive, this does not make them "safe." MDMA, also known as 'Elation,' is a psychoactive substance found in glues, aerosols, and smoke bombs [11,3]. Drugs like cannabis and LSD, on the other hand, have never harmed anyone due to an accident.
- **Diseases Caused by Drugs.** Only one component of the drug-disease relationship is well-known: the link between drug use and Transmitted infections. Technique-Specific Disease is a type of sickness in which the illness is caused by the way a drug is used rather than the drug itself. It's caused by heroin injections with infected needles, syringes, and combining containers shared by multiple people - what addicts call the "worksWhatever substance is injected – heroin, amphetamines, or even anabolic steroids by wrestlers – there is a risk of spreading not only HIV but also all Hepatitis viruses (B, C, and D), sepsis, abscesses, necrosis, and other illnesses if equipment is shared[12,8].
- **Material A second aspect of opioid disease that is often disregarded is disease. That is, illness caused by chemicals' direct adverse effects on various human organs. The brain and the liver are two examples of organ damage. — Beverages containing alcohol Marijuana and tobacco use cause lung and cardiovascular problems. Heart disease and strokes are three of the most popular causes of death. Cocaine – Heat exhaustion and liver injury Ecstasy is a noun that refers to euphoria.**
- **Humans must also examine the acute mental health disorders that cannabis can produce, the sadness caused by**

prolonged Ecstasy use, and the long-term mental illness that LSD can inflict[13].

- **Pregnancy and Drugs:** If a pregnant woman takes drugs, the chemical will be introduced to the unborn child in her uterus during important and vulnerable times in its cognitive functioning. Babies born addicted to opiates, physical defects associated to cocaine and alcohol, and altered intrauterine learning and expansion due to alcohol, nicotine, or cannabis exposure are all possibilities. Learning and Substance Abuse A poor impact on short-term memory and learning capacities is one of the most commonly publicised side effects of cannabis use, whether it's medicinal marijuana, resinous hash, or distilled hash oil[14]. Research work, as well as polls of juvenile cannabis users who are still hampered six weeks after stopping the substance, and surveys of adult daily users who consistently report memory and attention difficulties, have all revealed that cannabis impairs all evaluations of intellectual process.
- **Drugs and Accidents:** Following an amount of high industrial tragedies involving drugged personnel, numerous major corporations in the U.s have begun to explore the financial implications of drug use within their staff. As proven by the 1987 train disaster in Chase, Maryland, in which 16 people were killed and the probable reason was judged to be the train driver's use of cannabis, such drug use increases the risk of accidents [15]. A survey performed by the American Psychological Association, new employees who tested positive for cannabis in a pre-employment screen had 55 percent more industrial accidents, 85 percent greater injuries, and 78 percent more absenteeism than non-drug users[5] . Employees who tested positive for cocaine had a 145 percent greater rate of absenteeism and an 85 percent higher rate of injury. Employee drug use is expected to cost more than \$47 billion per year in the United States.
- **Drugs and Behavior:** Since many drug addicts, the relationship between drugs and behavior is complicated, most harmful component of their drug usage is their altered behavior when under the influence of the substance. The violence connected with taking whisky, is dangerous aspect of solvent addiction for most teenagers is the confused inebriated behavior that comes with it [16]. The delusional behavior linked with Amphetamine use is especially problematic given its expanding popularity in the 'Dance party' environment. For many young individuals, the expansion of uninterested, negative view and boldness can damage your cannabis.
- **Drugs and Crime:** Drug usage is commonly related to passionate and greedy criminality, according to popular belief. Because no substance is inherently criminogenic, the term "drug-related crime" is usually associated with greedy criminalities dedicated by opiate fanatics in earning money to commence bad thing. Because heroin is so expensive on the street, users often conduct robberies to get money for narcotics. Robberies sometimes involve violence and threats of violence, which is tend to diminish rather than develop or release aggressive violent tendencies[17].

According to research findings, the relationship between opiate and property offenses may not completely effective. The exorbitant cost of street opiates is without hesitation a major influence on many addicts' criminal activities.

However, studied much of the American literature and found that the wholesale of palliative users who are complicated in criminality had already established criminal careers before to starting to take drugs. According to a study conducted by[14], 61 percent of cocaine users in the area are arrested for criminalities prior to starting to use the substance. In November 1994, Drug-Link issued a summary of their findings[9]. The authors of this paper questioned the estimate that opiate or cocaine addicts committed half of all acquisitive crime in England and Wales. They discovered that heroin addicts in England and Wales raised between £58 million and £864 million through acquisitive crime to buy heroin. This estimate ranges from 1% to 21% of the total cost of acquisitive crime in England and Wales.

- **Drug and Violent Crime:** A report on drugs and crime in the United Kingdom revealed a substantial correlation between (smokable cocaine) and violent crime. This is most likely related to the uncertainty associated with long-term chemical use, such as cocaine and stimulant substances, which can lead to excessive violence[17-18]. These are potential concerns at this time/given the current levels of use of such medicines, and the dangers of associated with the depressing effects of sedatives like valium and flunitrazepam, which are prescribed for some morphine addicts.
- **Alcohol and Violence:** Common drug and alcohol are related with a higher likelihood of violence. According to the Royal College of Psychiatrists in the United Kingdom, alcohol stood complicated in up to 40 percent of stabbings and to 60 percent of attacks. Murdoch and colleagues discovered that majority of offenders were drunk at the time of the incident in a review of over 3,000 violent crimes recorded from 8 different nations[19]. As a result, they are now known as an alcohol having a direct and dose-dependent effect on human aggression, with a significant relationship between alcohol consumption and marital violence.

III. CONCLUSION

Impartial as the substances that people use varied, so do the hazards they face. New medications, new hazards, and new, more harmful ways of using existing drugs will all be part of the future. Attempting to forecast future patterns would be foolhardy. No one can forecast which drugs will be the drugs of the future, just as no one can predict the advent of heroin alternative, the introduction of Trance in the 1990. What is clear is that drugs will continue to wreak havoc on our country's most vulnerable and valued inhabitants, the youth. It is also certain that society's response will require a balanced blend of law enforcement, treatment, and education. Getting the balance right is critical to the society's sustained physical and intellectual comfort.

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